

ION BEAM SPUTTER DEPOSITION OF PIEZOELECTRIC ALN THIN FILMS

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ABSTRACT – The particle pillar sputtering process depends on the idea of particle strong communication. Contingent upon the episode energy, particles connect through Rutherford, feebly screened Coulomb and hard-circle collisions. The connection between the collision diameter and screening range is talked about for each situation. The development energy of Al-and AlN-slight movies in the structure of Dynamic Scaling Theory (DST) with the impact of receptive help of N^+/N_2^+ particles. Both the movies, Al and AlN have become on Si(100) substrates for 3, 5, 8 and 15 minutes. Their surface morphologies were recorded utilizing AFM and dissected to decide the development governing peculiarity that appears at every affidavit time. The assimilation spectra were gathered in close to typical frequency math in diffuse reflectance mode. Variation of ingestion coefficient (α) with photon energy ($h\nu$) is introduced as a function of development temperature. A broad examination of micro structural variations, the development of normal crystallite size and AlN stage development as a function of temperature was completed utilizing X-ray diffraction (XRD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). Positron annihilation spectroscopy is utilized to examine the presence of deformities in film microstructure.

Keywords: [power consumption, X-ray, spectroscopy, Films, ion beam.]

1. INTRODUCTION

Every material surface is presented to different environmental influences. The surface of a strong body is exposed to consumption and wear and connects with light and electromagnetic fields. According to the technological perspective the miniaturization of mechanic, electronic, optical and optoelectronic components forever builds the surface to volume proportion of the elaborate materials. In present day material science explicit surface properties subsequently gain expanding significance. Regardless, the ideal mechanical, optical chemical or electronic properties are frequently against the bulk properties which might be high mechanical soundness, simple assembling or low material expense. As a result of this reality a multitude

assuming High Tech components are composite materials which imply that the surface properties fundamentally contrast from the bulk properties. A model might be a mechanical part which needs to display high hardness (I. e. low wear under tribological load) as well as high break strength (I. e. high resistance against break engendering). A single material may not satisfy these requests. The arrangement of the issue can be a composite material comprising of a surface zone (coating) with high surface hardness and an intense bulk core.

Thin Film

- Dainty film is a layer that broadens limitlessly along any two directions yet confined along the third direction. The thickness is from a few nanometers to few micrometers. fundamental benefit of meager film technology:

- The reduction in size
- Tuning of materials' surface properties: reflection, absorption, hardness, abrasion resistance, corrosion, and electrical way of behaving
- Dainty films give cost reduction
- Miniaturization of the device

History if Thin Film Technology

In 1650, Observation and understanding of obstruction designs (e. g. oil on water) by R.Boyle, R.Hooke, I.Newton. In 1850, Development of first affidavit techniques (M.Faraday; W.Grove; T.A.Edison) and of methods of thickness determination (Arago, Fizeau; Wernicke; Wiener) Commercial presentation of electrochemistry (Galvanics) for gold plating of uniform-accessories.

1940: Industrial manufacturing of coatings for optical, electronically and mechanical applications (generally military). ~1965: Thin film technology creates to a fundamental piece of the mass manufacturing processes in semiconductor and optical industry. ~1990: Thin films of High Tc-Superconductors. ~1995: Thin film handling takes into consideration the fitting of microstructures of atomic and macroscopic dimensions („Quantum-Dots" by PVD, „Cu-technology" by electrochemistry applied to incorporated circuits). ~2000: Manufacturing of nanocrystalline materials with characterized synthesis and

structure for applications as defensive coatings and in tribological. Deposition of profoundly requested two and three dimensional items with sizes in the nm range. ~2004: Up scaling of complicated receptive coating processes for industrial applications (coatings on glass, warm administration) combinatorial investigation of ternary and quaternary material frameworks. ~2006: Investigation of organic coatings prompts the rise of organic electronics

(OLED, printable circuits). ~2010: Preparation and portrayal of the model two dimensional (2d) material, Grapheme. Presentation of dependable strong state contact screens to correspondence media (Smartphone). ~2015: Generation of heterostructures produced using 2d materials. Ways to deal with make adaptable electronic devices comprising of ultrathin materials.

Figure 1. Structure of Film

The properties of the films are basically overwhelmed by the structure of the film, however the mechanical and warm properties of films are connected with the response condition and deposition method.

The property of meager film by and large differs from the upsides of the actual boundaries of the materials in bulk structure as given beneath.

*Meager Films might be: *Not completely dense, *under stress, *Quasi-two dimensional, *Different imperfection structures from the bulk material, *strongly impacted by surface and connection point impacts.

These extraordinary properties can be because of their little thickness of few atomic layers up to micrometer esteem. This will change the optical, attractive, electrical, warm, mechanical and chemical properties. Table1 separates slim film properties into five essential classifications and gives illustration of regular applications inside every classification. The properties of the slight films can likewise be impacted by the high surface to volume proportion of the film much of the time the development and arrangement of slender film are impacted by the properties of the underlying substrate material.

Thin Film Property Category	Typical Applications
Optical	Reflective/ antireflective coatings Interference filters Decoration (color, luster) Optical memory discs (CDs, DVDs) Optical Waveguides
Magnetic	Memory discs (Hull discs and tapes)
Electrical	Insulation Conduction Semiconductor devices Piezoelectric drivers
Thermal	Barrier layers Heat sinks
Chemical	Barrier to diffusion or alloying Protection against oxidation or corrosion Gas/liquid sensors
Mechanical	Tribo logical (Wear-resistant) coatings Hardness Adhesion Micromechanics

Table 1. Properties and applications of thin films

Structure and Morphology of Thin Films

Thin-film microstructure and properties rely upon the development component, deposition boundaries (i.e., low temperature or fume pressure) and techniques we utilize during the manufacturing system. Microstructures comprise of three sorts:

- Amorphous: Forms an ideal glasslike cross section
- Polycrystalline: Forms nano/miniature crystallites of differing sizes
- Epitaxial thin films: Forms strong glasslike film with latticework.

Thin film applications rely heavily upon thin-film morphology, and that relies upon different variables. It incorporates deposition technique and molecule adsorption during film development. Additionally, the kind of material and the transition of fume and molecules influence the last morphology, development structure, and film thickness. For instance, thin films developed by means of fume deposition frequently include cylindrical structures.

Properties of Thin Films

There are a few properties that are vital for current thin film applications. The manufacturing system should notice specific circumstances and avoid potential risk, so it's not hurting the thin film applications subsequently.

While depositing thin films onto a substrate, fundamental contemplations incorporate characterization techniques and long-term execution of the improved properties. Thin-film coatings act uniquely in contrast to bulk material, and remaining stress during deposition can adjust the film's properties, such as causing abandons in the glasslike structure or epitaxial development.

Such stressors and the film's microstructure can adversely influence its mechanical properties, similar to hardness and yield. Substrate and film type (i.e., metallic films, covers, and semiconductors), immaculateness, and scaling adjust electrical properties, like lessening conductivity. Finally, the association between deposition boundaries and microstructure developments influences a thin film's optical properties.

Thin film deposition techniques

Two common deposition techniques:

Chemical deposition: A fluid precursor undergoes a chemical change at a solid surface, leaving a solid layer.

Physical deposition: Uses mechanical, electromechanical or thermodynamic means to produce a thin film of solid.

Particle shaft sputter deposition is one of the laid out techniques to store device-grade thin films. However it was first utilized in the last part of the 1960s, yet the emanation of target particles under the effect of lively nonpartisan or charged particles on the objective material has been a topic of investigation for over hundred years. The quick increment of interest in examining sputtering peculiarities over most recent couple of many years might be made sense of by the expanded acknowledgment of sputtering process in the field of controlled deposition of thin films of practically any material. By and large, sputtering is a cycle by which particles are launched out from a strong objective material because of bombardment of focus by fiery particles. The vivacious particles in

sputtering might be particles, unbiased molecules, electrons or photons. Since most significant and effective sputtering applications are performed under bombardment with particles, it is by and large characterized as the communication between lively episode particles and surface molecules of the objective. Particles impinging onto a strong can cause different particle strong communication impacts due to atomic and electronic energy losses caused by the striking particles. These occurrence particles set off collision cascades in the objective. At the point when such cascades backlash and arrive at the objective surface with energy more noteworthy than the surface restricting energy, a molecule would be shot out. In this way, the association between lively particles and iota's of the solids shapes the reason for the understanding of particle bar sputter deposition of thin films.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Jilani, A., Abdel-wahab, M. S., & Hammad, A. H. (2017). Advance Deposition Techniques for Thin Film and Coating. Meager films extraordinarily affect the advanced time of technology. Meager films are considered as the spine for cutting edge applications in different fields like optical gadgets, ecological applications, media communications gadgets, energy capacity gadgets, etc. The essential issue for all utilizations of slender films relies upon their morphology and steadiness. The morphology of the flimsy films strongly relies on deposition strategies. Slim films can be stored by the physical and chemical routes. In this part, we examine a few high level strategies and standards of thin-film depositions. The vacuum warm vanishing strategy, electron pillar dissipation, beat layer deposition, direct current/radio recurrence magnetron sputtering and chemical course deposition frameworks will be talked about exhaustively.

2. Kashif Tufail Chaudhary (2020) proposed Thin Film Deposition: Solution Based Approach The wet chemical processing opens the method for saving slim film no sweat for various materials. Fluid film deposition includes the use of a fluid forerunner on a substrate which is then changed over completely to the expected covering material in a resulting post-treatment step. Different non-vacuum arrangement based deposition procedures have been created to develop dainty films with high proficiency and functionality. Turn covering is a successful strategy for slim film fabrication because of its low expense, consistency, less perilous, and capacity of simple increasing. Plunge covering is another basic, financially savvy course with the feasibility to increase for business creation. The covering might be exposed to additional intensity therapy to wear out remaining mixtures and initiate crystallization of the functional oxides. Spray covering is a promising strategy to develop flimsy film in examination and industry to get ready dainty and thick films.

3. Xie, T., Xie, G., Du, H., Zhou, Y., Xie, F., Jiang, Y., & Tai, H. (2016) proposed The Fabrication and Optimization of Thin-Film Transistors Based on Poly (3-Hexylthiophene) Films for Nitrogen Dioxide Detection. Poly (3-

hexylthiophene) (P3HT) films were used as dynamic layers in base contact natural slight film semiconductor (OTFT) gas sensors to detect nitrogen dioxide (NO₂). The OTFT gas sensors with thinner P3HT film showed more modest pattern float, higher reaction to NO₂ gas of a specific concentration and bigger responsiveness enhancement. The ongoing difference in OTFT gas sensors in light of the P3HT film was clarified by doping of the semiconductor due for the oxidizing NO₂. Attributable to the vicinity of the air/P3HT connection point to the charge transport divert in slim film, the reaction enhancement was noticed. Besides, the benchmark float and selectivity were worked on by diminishing the P3HT thickness. These improvements made the OTFT gas sensors promising for environmental and industrial applications.

4. He, H., Liu, Y., Yan, B. (2018) et.al proposed Analytical Drain Current Model for Amorphous and Polycrystalline Silicon Thin-Film Transistors at Different Temperatures Considering Both Deep and Tail Trap States. In the channel current model, it is accepted that the trapped transporter concentration is a lot higher than the free transporter concentration considering both profound snare states and tail trap states in the energy hole of the slight film. The model is substantial in both subthreshold or more limits systems and is checked by the accessible exploratory information at various temperatures. With respect to the a-Si and poly-Si TFTs, the channel current model, which is reasonable for both the sub threshold system and the above-limit system, hasn't been accounted for. TFTs have been reached out to the a-Si and poly-Si TFTs and can portray the dynamic energy characteristics of the channel current.

5. Ou, Deng, Xu, Chen, & Wang. (2016) proposed Three-dimensional fin-shaped dual-gate photosensitive a-Si:H thin-film transistor for low dose X-ray imaging. This work investigates a clever double door photosensitive nebulous silicon (a-Si: H) flimsy film semiconductor (TFT) for low-level light detection. To upgrade transporter assortment and light ingestion while keeping up with good exchanging execution, a three-layered (3D) balance formed channel is planned and verified. Because of field fortifying especially close by the contact locales, the responsiveness boundary $\gamma_{Dark} = -0.84$ is acquired. Subsequently, the gadget will in general have a more extensive dynamic reach contrasted and the past Pi-formed and planar designs [1, 2]. The wide dynamic reach and high awareness make the 3D balance molded TFTs promising for low-portion backhanded transformation X-imaging.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Experimental set-up of IBSD framework and its fundamental part are displayed in the principal deposition chamber is furnished with a turbo molecular pump (TMP) supported by a parchment pump to clear it to the base pressure of 2×10^{-7} mbar. A titanium sublimation pump (TSP) is likewise given in the fundamental deposition chamber for particular expulsion of other foundation receptive gases like oxygen (O₂ and H₂O-vapors). The heap lock chamber is pumped by a different TMP supported by a parchment pump which generally

accomplishes a base pressure of 5×10^{-8} mbar. For deposition, the substrate is stacked into the heap lock chamber and is transferred into the fundamental chamber with a straight transfer bar through an isolation valve. This forestalls the deterioration of base vacuum of the principal deposition chamber and keeps up with air immaculateness within the chamber. To empower orderly monitoring of deposition parameters, the chamber is furnished with a number of estimating instruments, for example, quartz crystal thickness screen, leftover gas analyzer, and high vacuum checks. A substrate controller is likewise given to allow substrate warming and rotation during deposition.

Ion - Solid Interaction: Mechanism of Sputtering

Two hypothetical models have been proposed for sputtering:

- Warm vaporization theory: The surface of the objective is adequately warmed to be disintegrated because of the bombardment of energetic ions.
- Momentum transfer theory: Surface molecules of the objective are discharged when active snapshots of occurrence particles are transferred to target iotas living on surface.

The warm vaporization theory was upheld by Hippel in 1926, Sommermeyer in 1935 and Townes in 1944 because of their experimental observations of the Kundsens cosine emission distribution. Around then, the warm vaporization theory was viewed as the main component. The momentum transfer theory was first proposed by Stark in 1908 and Compton in 1934. The definite examinations by Wehner in 1956, including the observation of spot designs in single crystal sputtering, recommended that the main component isn't warm vaporization yet the momentum transfer the warm vaporization theory was upheld by Hippel in 1926, Sommermeyer in 1935 and Townes in 1944 because of their experimental observations of the Kundsens cosine emission distribution. Around then, the warm vaporization theory was viewed as the main system. The momentum transfer theory was first proposed by Stark in 1908 and Compton in 1934. The itemized examinations by Wehner in 1956, including the observation of spot designs in single crystal sputtering, recommended that the main system isn't warm vaporization however the momentum transfer.

The nuclei of the objective particles are screened by electron mists. The kind of collision between an episode molecule and the objective is determined by occurrence ion energy and the level of electron screening. The interaction likely between the occurrence molecule of mass m and a 'stationary' grid iota of mass M is the screened Coulomb expected between the two nuclei. This potential has the structure:

$$V(r) = \frac{Z_1 * Z_2}{r} e^2 \exp\left(\frac{-r}{a}\right)$$

Where r is the separation of the two atomic charges, a is the screening span of the orbital electrons, and Z_1 and Z_2 re the atomic numbers of the episode particle and the objective molecule, individually

For the screening range a , which can be decided to fit the Thomas-Fermi field, Bohr proposed the relation.

$$a = \frac{a_0}{\left(Z_1^{\frac{2}{3}} + Z_2^{\frac{2}{3}}\right)^{1/2}}$$

In this expression, a_0 is the Bohr radius of the hydrogen particle ($= 0.57 \times 10^{-8}$ cm). Another significant scattering boundary is the collision diameter b . The boundary b is given by the relation

$$b = \frac{2Z_1Z_2e^2}{\mu v^2}$$

Weak-Screening Collisions

If the kinetic energy E of the incident particle lies within the energy range $E_A < E < E_B$, the screening of the nuclei by the orbital electrons becomes significant. As far as possible E_A is given by the relation

$$E_A = 2E_R Z_1 Z_2 \left(Z_1^{\frac{2}{3}} + Z_2^{\frac{2}{3}}\right)^{1/2} \frac{m + M}{M}$$

The mean recoil energy of the struck atom is:

$$\bar{E} = E_d \left(\frac{E_B}{E}\right) \ln\left(1 + \frac{4E^2}{E_A^2}\right)$$

Ion Beam Sputter Deposition System: Experimental Set-up

The principal deposition chamber is outfitted with a turbo molecular pump (TMP) upheld by a parchment pump to empty it to the base pressure of 2×10^{-7} mbar. A titanium sublimation pump (TSP) is additionally given in the fundamental deposition chamber for specific expulsion of other foundation responsive gases like oxygen (O_2 and H_2O -vapors). The heap lock chamber is pumped by a different TMP upheld by a parchment pump which typically accomplishes a base pressure of 5×10^{-8} mbar. For deposition, the substrate is stacked into the heap lock chamber and is transferred into the principal chamber with a direct transfer pole through an isolation valve. This forestalls the deterioration of base vacuum of the primary deposition chamber and keeps up with climatic immaculateness within the chamber. To empower methodical monitoring of deposition parameters, the chamber is furnished with a number of estimating instruments, for example, quartz crystal thickness screen, remaining gas analyzer, and high vacuum measures. A substrate controller is likewise given to allow substrate warming and rotation during deposition.

Composition optimization by XPS

Impact of substrate temperature on the compositional development of AlN meager films was additionally explored to lay out the stage part of AlN thin films formed during reactive assistive IBSD process. For this purpose, thin film samples were prepared at different substrate temperatures viz. RT, 100°C and 500°C. XPS (M/s Specs, Germany) analysis was carried out on these thin films to obtain the information about AlN phase formation and its subsequent quantification on the surface as well as 50 nm underneath the surface. In addition, entrainment of nitrogen and oxygen in their various chemical forms like Al-O and N-Al-O were also estimated by quantifying their

respective phase fractions. For this, a monochromatic X-ray source of aluminum with $K\alpha = 1486.6$ eV operated at 15 KV and 22 mA was employed. A concentric hemispherical analyzer of 150 mm diameter was used to analyze the photoelectrons with an electron takeoff angle of 90°. During measurement, base pressure of the spectrometer was kept constant at 2.3×10^{-10} mbar.

Growth Kinetics of Aluminum Nitride (AlN) Thin Films by DST

The progressions in morphological elements and commonness of specific surface peculiarities at various phases of AlN thin film growth supported by receptive help of N^+ and N_2^+ ions are thought in this section. Such a growth situation frequently brings about a cycle condition which is a long way from equilibrium. Growth overseeing static and dynamic scaling types were determined by comparative calculations previously utilized if there should arise an occurrence of Al thin film growth without ion help. DST formalism has been utilized to disentangle the overseeing peculiarities behind ion helped thin film growth.

TEM measurements

A precise report on miniature primary evolution of AlN thin films kept at various substrate temperatures was done utilizing high resolution TEM (Libra 200FE/HR-TEM). Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) examples of these films have been examined to determine the evolution of the crystallographic stages and normal crystallite size (d) at various substrate temperatures. Miniature underlying information of the films is portrayed in figure 4.5(A) which shows dull field pictures procured by TEM for tests saved at various substrate temperatures. A cautious examination of these dim field pictures uncover that the films stored at RT to 200°C substrate temperature have an irregular atomic organization and need long reach coordination in its microstructure

This observation is additionally affirmed by the selected area electron diffraction (SAED) designs displayed in the inset of each picture up to 200°C. Notwithstanding, for films stored at 300°C substrate temperature, beginning of crystallization are seen which progresses with additional expansion in substrate temperature and slowly develops into a nanocrystalline microstructure at 400°C and 500°C. For clearness, scarcely any regions of interest (RoI) in these dim field pictures are shown by splendid rings. Nanocrystalline microstructure of these films was additionally examined by obtaining SAED designs at every substrate temperature from 300°C to 500°C

AlN – Thin Film Deposition

Deposition of AlN-thin films was carried out after achieving a base pressure better than 4×10^{-6} mbar. Working pressure of the chamber was maintained at 2×10^{-4} mbar while substrate temperature was kept constant at 500°C. Films were grown for 3, 5, 8 and 15 minutes of time duration. During deposition, the metal atom flux was provided by sputtering Al target with Ar^+ ion beam having energy of 500 eV. Reactively assistive flux of N^+ and N_2^+

ions was supplied directly to the substrate surface from the end-Hall ion source operated at energy of 100 eV.

Optimization of Deposition Time

By virtue of above observations, assisted ion energy was optimized at 90 eV with main ion beam energy of 500 eV used for sputtering. As specific features appeared on the film surface at 500o C and similar phase fraction of AlN is formed at 400o C and 500o C, substrate temperature was optimized at 400o C for further optimization of deposition time to obtain quartzite hexagonal AlN in thin film form. For this, deposition time was varied as 3, 5, 8, 15, 30, 45 and 60 minutes. It is found that for short deposition times from 3 to 15 minutes, cubic phase of AlN is formed. For films deposited for 3 and 5 minutes, full coverage of substrate surface could not take place. Thus a peak pertaining to Si miscut plane (311) also appears along with a sharp peak which is considered to occur due to some anomalous scattering as reported in literature.

The full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the rocking curve provides a direct estimation of relative disorientation of the grains. In figure 4.12, the FWHM of the rocking curve is found to be 0.0417o which indicates that the crystals were slightly disoriented with respect to each other. Thus, AlN thin films grown on Si(100) substrates for 60 minutes at 500o C were found to exhibit high degree of texture along a-axis.

Deposition of AlN Thin Films

AlN thin films were deposited on 10 mm X 10 mm Si (100) substrates by reactive IBSD. The base pressure of the chamber was 4×10^{-7} mbar while working pressure was maintained at 4×10^{-4} mbar during deposition. Films were grown at different substrate temperatures varying from RT to 500o C in steps of 100o C. During deposition, the required metal atom flux was provided by sputtering an Al-target (99.999% pure) with an Ar+ ion beam extracted from a 6 cm RF ion source with energy of 500 eV. Concomitantly, an End-Hall type ion source was used to deliver an assistive reactive flux consisting of N+ /N₂ + ions at 90 eV directly to the substrate surface. The thickness of the films was measured ex-situ using a surface profilometer (Veeco, USA) and estimated to be ~114 nm for all the samples.

Calculation of Optical Band Gap Energy (E_g)

The fundamental absorption in a material takes place either by excitonic process or by band-to-band transition during interaction of photon with matter. Herein, two types of transitions are possible at this fundamental edge: direct and indirect. Both these advances include connection of photon with an electron in the valence band which accordingly gets energized into the conduction band across the key band gap. However, in the case of an indirect transition, simultaneous interaction with lattice vibration also takes place. The appearance of optical band-gap in thin films is greatly affected by its micro structural constituents like short-range co-ordination, crystallite size and type of defects present in the system etc.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

Figure 2 Tauc's plots

Tauc's plots to estimate the optical band gap energy at each substrate temperature. At RT, E_g is found to be 5.08 eV. As the temperature of the substrate is increased to 100o C, E_g increases subsequently to 5.13 eV. Maintaining this rising trend with further increase in substrate temperature E_g becomes 5.19 eV, 5.20 eV and 5.21 eV, respectively, for 300o C, 400o C and 500o C.

Figure 3 variation

Comparative variation of E_g with net $E_u + E_t$. When fitted with a straight line, intercept of the linear fit (~ 6.24 eV) represents the optical band gap energy of the films when there is no disorder in their microstructure.

Film Reels	THIN FILM	ALN THIN FILMS
100	\$200	\$180
200	\$350	\$320
300	\$400	\$350
400	\$500	\$400

Table 2. Cost effective

Figure 4. Comparison Chart of Cost effective

The comparison chart and table shows the Thin Film and ALN Thin Film cost effective. That's also production effective compare than other Films.

CONCLUSION

To deposit AlN thin films with minimum contamination, deposition parameters were systematically varied. Microstructural investigation was carried out to confirm the formation of AlN phase. Surface composition analysis was used to pin-point undesirable constituents and arrives upon a set of parameters that leads to the deposition of high quality AlN thin film. Then for an 8 minutes deposition, bulk diffusion dominates to fill the valleys and other remnant irregularities on the surface and covers a larger area on the substrate surface. Both plastic flow and bulk diffusion act as principle smoothening phenomena. For longer deposition times of 15 minutes, same set of smoothening phenomena operates to achieve a continuous film with no uncovered channels.

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